

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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Analysis reports after carrying out the
research across countries in reception
centres and other experiential
environments

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Summary

This report presents qualitative and quantitative results from the IMMERSE data collection for unaccompanied minors, refugees and asylum seekers. The report focuses on the qualitative research carried out between March and December 2021 in the six IMMERSE countries. And it includes an overview of the quantitative survey data results collected for 1,592 children who are Unaccompanied Minors, Refugees or Asylum Seekers between June 2021 and July 2023. These children represent 6.5% of the total IMMERSE survey sample, and 11.9% of the migrant-background sample obtained.

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Analysis reports after carrying out the research across countries in reception centres and other experiential environments (non-school environments)

1 Executive summary

This report presents the results from the IMMERSE qualitative and quantitative data collection with unaccompanied minors, refugees, and asylum seekers. The report focuses on the qualitative research carried out between March 2021 and March 2023 in the six IMMERSE countries. And it includes an overview of the quantitative survey data results collected for 1,592 unaccompanied minors, refugees or asylum seekers between June 2021 and July 2023.¹

Acknowledging the various obstacles of access to formal education (see D.3.4), the qualitative research component of IMMERSE was designed to focus on groups of migrant children -mainly Unaccompanied Minors - whose experiences may not have been fully captured in the IMMERSE large-scale quantitative survey, as they frequently go under-represented in large-scale data collections. Research partners identified non-formal environments in their particular contexts where children more frequently excluded from national education systems could participate in the research to ensure their voices would be heard. 13 qualitative case studies were conducted in six member states, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain. The case studies involve 91 child and youth participants in total, comprising mainly unaccompanied children, who in many cases are also refugees or asylum seekers, but also include newly arrived migrant children, or other first and second-generation migrant children in vulnerable situations, aged 9-21 years old. Children were interviewed mostly in informal educational settings, in NGO premises, in reception centres or other shelters for unaccompanied minors.

The findings indicate that school and educational experiences are important for creating a sense of belonging and providing opportunities to make friends and develop language skills and is central for these children's integration processes. Moreover, according to the quantitative results, these children have a high level of trust in their schools and education settings and felt supported by their teachers. Notwithstanding these positive findings, some difficulties in accessing appropriate education, and experiences of bullying and racism in education settings were also identified.

¹ These children represent 6.5% of the total IMMERSE survey sample, and 11.9% of the migrant-background sample obtained.

The quantitative study also found there was slightly higher levels of engagement with learning and language support for these two migrant groups compared to other migrant children in the research. However, the findings on host language competencies for Refugee and Asylum-seeking children indicate the need to provide additional supports to this group to support language proficiency. Also, Refugee and Asylum-seeking children had lower levels of institutional trust in health and justice (including police) institutions than other migrant and non-migrant groups in the research. Legal and administration challenges encountered by the participants, particularly Unaccompanied Minors, included obtaining residency and citizenship and having to follow the rules of accommodation centres, but citizenship was a valued goal for the freedoms and benefits it would bring. The experiences of these recently arrived migrant children highlighted the fact the disruptive impact of frequent moves but also for they were generally positive about their experiences of mainstream school system once settled.

The research found that friendships provide a sense of security and belonging for children and young people, with education settings seen as central to building these peer relations. The importance of children and young people's families were highlighted along with the tensions between cultural and religious norms of the host country and the 'home' country. Recognizing the influence of age, gender, and migration status is essential for effective support and the successful socio-educational integration of migrant children. Final conclusions are drawn based on both the primary qualitative and quantitative data collection and the literature.

2 Education experiences of unaccompanied minors, refugees and asylum seeker children

Unaccompanied Minors and children with refugee profiles have fled their countries under particularly difficult conditions and they continue facing multiple challenges upon arrival in host countries (Bhabha and Abel, 2019). Their integration perspectives depend on many factors, which will be discussed below. This section provides a brief overview of the situation of Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-seeking Children considering both formal and informal education.

2.1 Formal education settings

All six IMMERSE participating countries have an obligation to respect international and EU Law provisions and facilitate access to education for migrant children. Additionally, as dictated by EU

Law (Article 14 (2) of the Reception Conditions Directive), children and young people of compulsory school age seeking international protection, have the same rights and obligations to participate in education as those born in the host country (Noorani et al, 2019). Regarding children granted international protection, Member States should grant them full access to the education system under the same conditions as nationals. (Article 27 (1) of the Qualification Directive).

However, despite legislative provisions guaranteeing all children's right to formal compulsory education, there is evidence that this right is not always implemented in practice for newly arrived migrant children, particularly asylum seekers, for unaccompanied minors (especially the older ones), or for certain under-represented categories of first and second generation of migrant children. As stated by UNHCR/UNICEF/IOM, although all children's fundamental right to basic education is recognized under international and European human rights law, as well as EU law, 'in practice the type, quality and duration of schooling offered to asylum-seeking, refugee and migrant children depends more on where they are in the migrant/asylum process than on their educational needs' (UNHCR, UNICEF, IOM 2019: 4). Furthermore, categorisations such as 'newly arrived refugee children', 'unaccompanied minors', 'asylum seekers' can be misleading, as immigration processes across European countries vary and children's realities can intersect in a complex way with these categories.

Most EU countries have been facing challenges in guaranteeing equal access and integrating newly arriving refugees and immigrants and in particular Unaccompanied Minors into formal education for several decades. But these challenges have intensified since 2015 with the arrival of larger numbers of refugees and asylum seekers (Koehler & Schneider, 2019). And even though all six IMMERSE participating countries formally respect the legal obligation under international and EU Law to facilitate access to formal education for migrant children, there are several barriers that result in inadequate access and low enrolment levels, especially for newly arrived and for Unaccompanied Minors. Furthermore, formal educational systems of host countries and traditional cognitive teaching models are often inadequate to address the needs of refugee children and children with a migrant background.

FRA (2019) highlighted the challenges associated with the waiting times for newly arrived migrant children in accessing compulsory schooling, particularly in Greece². Other challenges in Greece

² Other important surveys, i.e. in Greece by the GCR -Terre des Hommes, 2022, or the Greek Ombudsman, *Εκπαιδευτική ένταξη παιδιών που διαβιούν σε Δομές και ΚΥΤ του Υπουργείου Μετανάστευσης & Ασύλου* (in Greek) and of "Guardian Teachers", 2022, show that basic barriers for UAM is the inability to enroll due to insufficient slots in schools or the inability to be enrolled if they arrive after the first school semester was already concluded. Schools cited the upcoming end of the school year and the inability to attend class and refused registration. The greatest difficulty was in the high

include different regional policies regarding access to public schools and most children on the Eastern Aegean islands not having access to formal education (FRA, 2020). In Germany FRA (2020) highlighted the situation of children in temporary accommodation centres who have had difficulties accessing school since they cannot register for school allocation, as it is unclear if they will remain in the federal state.

While access to education for compulsory school age children regardless of migratory status is similar in all partner countries, for migrant children and young people, particularly undocumented migrants and/or asylum seekers, who are beyond the compulsory school age (15+) the situation is worse. In Belgium for example some voluntary oriented compensatory programmes require resident permits which may preclude certain migrant young people from participation (Noorani et al. 2019, p. 8). Lack of legal status was also highlighted as a significant barrier by Unaccompanied Minors participating in the research in Spain, as well as in Greece. There is also evidence that migrant children, especially those who arrive after compulsory school age, often experience barriers accessing second level education (FRA 2019 and Anadoxoi Ekpaideytikoi 2022). In Italy, the FRA (2020) has reported cases of long waiting times for enrolment of children in compulsory school (in some cases between 8 and 18 months). Additionally, there were some concerns that schools were reluctant to take children over 15 who did not speak Italian and these children then became the responsibility of the adult education system – CPIAs (Provincial Centres for Adult Instruction). In Germany delays in the assessment of migrant students' qualifications led to students being placed in incorrect levels of education and delay in school enrolment was identified as contributing to school drop-out (ibid).

In addition, for a variety of reasons, across all EU+ Member States, except for the United Kingdom, children and youth born outside the EU+ are over-represented among those who leave school early. Overall, early school leaving among children born outside the EU+ is almost twice as high compared to native-born children (25.4% vs. 11.5%). This gap is most pronounced in Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, and Spain (UNICEF, 2019). In Greece, in particular, the dropout rate is particularly high among Unaccompanied Minors above the age of 15 in high school.

schools and in the secondary schools In the primary schools there were no problems and in the secondary schools there were a few difficulties. It should be noted that compulsory education in Greece includes primary education and the secondary grade. The high school, which is the Lyceum level (GEL and EPAL) is not compulsory. The highest percentage, 58%, of children not able to enroll in schools was in Attica, usually due their late arrival in the shelters and also because the EPAL (professional education) has only a few places and while the majority of the unaccompanied children in Greece are 15-17 year old. This explains why, UAM older than 15yrs are often enrolled at secondary education and therefore were included in the relevant data surveys of IMMERSE. See Marouda, Solidarity, 2019, Marouda, 2020

2.2 Informal education settings

Non-formal education programmes provided to refugee and migrant children vary across Europe. They may be offered as supplementary to formal education or separate to them. They often supplement formal education, tend to focus on the practical and can contribute to broadening the child's development (Sirius, 2018). Sometimes, it is suggested that they are the only viable education option for refugee children (Maldonado, 2017). Non-formal education, often provided by NGOs to newly arrived refugee children, may have a positive impact through focusing on addressing psychological barriers refugee children can face, in supporting their learning the language of the host country and initiate a smooth integration process and school performance (Sirius 2018).

Sometimes refugee and migrant children are not given the chance to attend formal education upon arrival for a variety of reasons, ranging from complex intersections between immigration status and educational bureaucracies, non-availability of appropriate school places, and administrative structures. These challenges are compounded for children who are outside compulsory school age (UNHCR UNICEF IOM 2019). Lack of host country's language knowledge, insufficient number of places in schools or even isolated locations of refugee camps away from urban areas can make non-formal education their only option. However, it is important to emphasise that non-formal education provided in refugee camps and centres for refugee children and Unaccompanied Minors is best considered as short term, because in the long term it has the potential to deprive children of interaction with local communities and can delay integration in host countries (Sirius, 2018). Furthermore, it is worth considering the content of these programmes. Non-formal education programmes have the flexibility of not having to follow national education curricula (ibid). Non-formal education provided in refugee camps, tend to consist of language classes including host country's language and English, as well as Maths (Koehler and Schneider, 2019). They might also include recreational and cultural activities and sports (Sirius, 2018). However, if continued, in the longer term, children are at risk of being deprived of the chance to follow national curricula, which is crucial for continuation of their studies in the host country.

3 Methodology

This section outlines the methodological approaches that were employed to assess the socio-educational integration of unaccompanied minors and refugee and asylum-seeking children in the

IMMERSE partner countries.³ While IMMERSE quantitative data methodology largely focused on schools as primary sampling units to reach a representative sample of children and educators, a more encompassing strategy was required to represent unaccompanied and refugee children, considering the identified difficulties for them to access formal education upon arrival (UNHCR, UNICEF, IOM 2019). This strategy involved accessing this population through non-formal education settings and other experiential environments (such as reception centres).

Two different approaches were implemented. On the one hand, these non-formal education settings and experiential environments were included in the quantitative data collection, complementing the main school-based sampling strategy, as they were more likely to be otherwise underrepresented (as usual in data collections encompassing larger populations). On the other hand, specific qualitative research was conducted in order to include their voices in IMMERSE research.

Conducting qualitative research with migrant children excluded from national education systems was a significant challenge for the research partners. Qualitative research in sensitive environments is generally a difficult process for researchers given challenges in maintaining boundaries, developing rapport and in managing emotions (Rodham, 1998). Data collection can be an intense experience, especially if the topic has to do with stressful human experiences. Addressing what makes children happy or sad and asking them to share their experiences requires going deep into other people's lives, sometimes at a time of crisis and stress (Glesne & Peshkin, 1992). Sime (2015) concludes that child-centred, qualitative research has clear advantages in giving migrant children a voice and informing current policy, practice and debates on global migration and social justice. However, researchers need to be mindful of migrant children's position within their families and society overall and think of their participation as often hedged around by constraints and control. Although IMMERSE research teams faced these and other challenges while conducting qualitative research with migrant and refugee children in experiential learning environments and reception centres, they appreciated the fact that as children were often marginalized and vulnerable, participation in this research provided them with an opportunity to be listened to by a person who really did want to hear their story.

3.1 Qualitative Case Study Methodology

³ See D3.4 for an in-depth overview of the quantitative data methodology.

Research partners identified non-formal environments where children excluded from national education systems could participate in the research. Each research partner completed two case studies, with one of these focusing specifically on Unaccompanied Minors, who are considered a particularly vulnerable group. As outlined above (Section 2), Unaccompanied Minors often face obstacles accessing formal education. According to UNHCR/UNICEF/IOM (2021) 71% of migrant children coming to Europe are unaccompanied and 30% are over 15 years old, which is when education becomes non-obligatory.

A total of **13 case studies were completed involving 91 child and youth participants** aged 9-21. These participants comprised in most cases unaccompanied minors (who are frequently refugees or asylum-seekers), but also newly arrived migrant children, and other first and second-generation migrant children in vulnerable situations such as Roma children.⁴ Table 1 outlines the participant sample and settings (including age and gender) in each IMMERSE country and the research methods employed in each case study (further details on the research settings can be found in Appendix 1). Data collection took place between April 2021 and March 2023.

Table 1. WP3 qualitative research participant details (participant profile, setting and methods)

Partner	No of Case studies	Profile of Migrant children included (age, gender, status etc)	Setting	Qualitative methods employed
UCC Ireland	2	1. Migrant young people – 2 UAMs and 1 refugee youth (3). Age range: 18-19 yrs. Gender: 1 female and 2 males	Government funded Youth and Education Service for newly arrived young people from refugee and migrant backgrounds before entering mainstream education.	Semi-structured focus group and individual interview, photovoice, mapping.
		2. Migrant children (first and second generation) Roma children (13) Age range: 9-13 yrs. Gender: all female	NGO for Traveller and Roma rights offering a programme for Roma children.	
SCIT Italy	3	1. Young people with migrant backgrounds (first and second generations) (6) Age range: 14-17 yrs. Gender: 3 female, 3 male	non-formal education environment hosting a long-term programme open to children from mixed	Semi-structured interviews, focus group, dairying, photovoice.

⁴ Each research partner completed two case studies, with one of these focusing specifically on Unaccompanied Minors (except in the case of Italy, where 3 case studies were conducted). In the case of one partner (Comillas, Spain) a number of staff supporting the migrant young people were interviewed.

		<p>2. Young people with migrant backgrounds (first and second generations) (2) Age range: 14-17 yrs. Gender breakdown: all male</p> <p>3. UAMs (4) Age range: 16-21 yrs. Gender: all male</p>	<p>background. Offers reception, study support activities, workshops. Legal, psychological, paediatric and parenting supports are offered to the parents.</p> <p>Two non-formal ed. environments offering long term educational supports.</p> <p>Non-formal ed. organization for the protection and integration of UAMs and newly arrived migrant children.</p>	
ACE Belgium	2	<p>1. Newly arrived migrant children from Syria (5) Age range: 10- 18 yrs. Gender breakdown: 3 Female (16,14,12), 2 Male (15, 15).</p> <p>2. Newly arrived migrant children from Ukraine, Rwanda, Columbia, Spain (5) Age range: 12-18yrs Gender: 2 female; 3 male</p>	<p>Non-profit organisation to aid the integration of migrants through sports, social and cultural activities.</p> <p>OKAN Unit attached to a secondary school</p>	photovoice
PANTEION Greece	2	<p>1. Newly arrived migrant children, and refugee and asylum seeker children (5) Age range: 14 to 17 yrs. Gender: 2 male, 3 female</p> <p>2. UAMs, newly arrived migrant children, and refugee and asylum seeker children (6) Age range: 14 to 17 yrs. Gender: all male</p>	<p>Non-profit organisation to aid the integration of newly arrived refugees through psychosocial services provision.</p>	Focus Group Discussions, Workshops
COMILLAS Spain	2	<p>1. UAMs in reception centres for foster care (37: 29 minors + 8 staff) Age range: 16-18 yrs. (UAMs). Gender: UAMs: 29 Males. Staff: 7 females, 1 male.</p> <p>2. UAMs in public residential care centre. (17: 8 youths + 7 staff) Age range: 16-17 yrs. (UAMs).</p>	<p>Foundation providing reception and care circuit for UAMs on behalf of the Catalan Government.</p> <p>Public residential care centre.</p>	Focus groups, In-depth interviews, Participant observation.

		Gender: UAMs: all male. Staff: 5 female, 3 male.	
DOZ Germany	2	<p>1. Refugee and asylum seeker children (4) Age range: 12- 14 yrs. Gender: 2 female, 2 male</p> <p>2. Refugee children, Syria (5) Age range: 11-15 yrs. Gender: 3 female; 2 male</p>	<p>NGO promoting intercultural coexistence with a variety of educational and cultural events/ workshops and social counselling.</p> <p>Group of children followed up from survey.</p> <p>Focus Group & Photovoice; Brainstorm mapping; co-creation of interview guide for focus group.</p>

3.1.1 Qualitative Research Methods

The explicitly rights-based and participatory approaches to the research were informed by the UNCRC and the Lundy model of participation (Lundy, 2007). Partners were encouraged to put a strong focus on the participation of children throughout the qualitative research process including their involvement as co-researchers aligned with Article 12 CRC (Alderson, 2012; Cuevas-Parra, 2021) and using specific child-friendly methods that help children to express themselves (Beazley et al., 2009) in line with Article 13 CRC. These could include focus groups, photovoice, journalling and mapping. The case studies were completed between 2021-2023 following an overall methodological framework, including Study Information and Assent forms for participant recruitment (see Appendix 2) as well as a Template for returning completed case studies (see Appendix 3).

Most research partners carried out a combination of focus groups and individual interviews (see Appendix 2 for details on each country’s strategy). Photovoice, mapping, diarying and participant observation were also employed as part of the qualitative research. Some partners co-created methods with the children and young people including, for example, the interview schedule for a subsequent focus group with young migrants (Appendix 4). The methods chosen varied with the composition of the research teams as well as the groups of young people engaging in the research. For example, it would be challenging to engage newly arrived migrant children in activities such as diarying and mapmaking. Training had emphasised that the research teams would ensure a physical and emotional “safe space” for the young people and establish adequate time for all participants in the discussion to share their thoughts. Feedback from the research partners

indicated that children and young people were excited to participate and express their opinions. They felt happy that they could share concerns and were empowered to do so.

Co-creation or co-production perceives participants as potential experts and creators of knowledge and can provide children and young people with a place in decision-making (Tisdall, 2017). There was significant co-creation with young people in the IMMERSE qualitative case studies. Photo-elicitation was used in six of the 13 case studies, where the young people were given relatively free reign to determine where they would take their pictures, what subjects they would take, and they were encouraged to express how they felt the photographs related to their lives. Most chose to send the photographs with their personal captions written by the photos explaining how it helped them feel like they belong.

Another example of co-creation was the work of the German partner Doz with a group of Syrian refugee children aged 11-15 years, in building the focus group discussion guide, which involved a number of engagements with the young people. The process as described by Doz is as follows: 'As a first step a kick-off was organised. Considering their experience with the questionnaires, the research team wanted to know their ideas about the IMMERSE Project. For that they prepared a big brainstorm map which they then filled. The inputs were clustered by the children. After that we informed the young people about the IMMERSE Project according to the clusters. The children decided they wanted a questionnaire before the big focus group discussion. Therefore, they listed subjects and questions for us to use instead of coming up with questions by ourselves.' (see Appendix 3 for Questionnaire)

Analysis of the qualitative data was undertaken using a systematic thematic method (Nowell et al., 2017). Verbatim quotes from the raw data transcriptions were used to support the write-up of findings in relation to the children and young people. In conducting the analysis, the authors aimed to identify the relevant issues/themes that related to the assumptions of the conceptual framework (Correa-Velez et al., 2010) already produced based in the literature review.

3.2 Quantitative Research: IMMERSE Large Scale Survey

The IMMERSE large-scale cross-country survey used specifically designed questionnaires to collect data from large numbers of migrant and refugee children in the six IMMERSE countries. The child participants in the survey were aged 7-18 years and the survey instruments were designed to be child-friendly and to allow for data harmonization across the six partner countries. A total of 24,000 children participated in the survey (60% of whom are from a refugee or migrant

background). Further details on the methodology and results of this survey, which covers 24,000 children (60% of whom are from a refugee or migrant background) can be found in D3.4. In this section we focus on the strategy for including unaccompanied minors and refugee and asylum-seeking children.

Specific efforts were made in the design and implementation of the survey fieldwork to identify and access non-formal educational sites and other experiential environments, such as reception centres, where both (1) **unaccompanied minors** and (2) **refugee and asylum-seeking children** (“refugee children” from now on) could be found, according to each national context.

- In Greece, Spain and Italy the research teams conducted fieldwork in reception centres or informal educational centres dedicated to unaccompanied minors. The resulting sample of **unaccompanied minors** is particularly significant in Greece and Spain.⁵
- In all countries **refugee children** were identified in the main school-based sample through the questionnaire,⁶ but the number of children reached in this manner was, as expected, quite low (409 across the six countries). With the inclusion of reception centres and informal educational centres dedicated to refugee children, a total of 914 additional children were reached out, thus providing a more robust picture of the situation in all six countries and highlighting the importance of including these sites to reach these groups of migrant children.⁷

In total, a sample was obtained of **1,592 children** who are unaccompanied minors or/and refugees or asylum seekers, representing 6.5% of the total IMMERSE survey sample, and 11.9% of the migrant-background sample. Figure below depicts the distribution per country and type of site.

⁵ The questionnaires did not identify unaccompanied minors, as this is a sensitive matter raising important ethical and methodological concerns. So, these were only identified at the level of sites (i.e. sites where information was collected exclusively for this population). This means we could not identify unaccompanied minors among the migrant-background children in the general sample (although they are likely represent very marginal numbers in any case).

⁶ Questions about administrative status were included in the parents’ questionnaire for all children. However, due the low response rate among parents, already evident in the piloting phase, this question was introduced also in the older children’s questionnaires. This question has delivered data consistent with children’s individual characteristics in other parts of the questionnaire in most of the cases. Although this information must still be treated with caution, as legal status is always complex to measure even among adult populations, children who have declared themselves to be refugees/asylum seekers show a consistent pattern that indicate a high degree of reliability of the information. Nonetheless, the exclusion of this question from the younger children’s questionnaire means we could not identify refugee and asylum seekers among the smaller children (7-10).

⁷ This was particularly important in Ireland, Italy, Greece and Belgium, where children from non-formal sites represent over three quarters of their refugee/asylum-seeker samples.

Fig. 1. Number of Children per country and type site

It is important to note that there is a substantial overlap between the considered categories, particularly in Greece and Italy, where all unaccompanied minors in the sample are also refugees or asylum seekers. The situation is different in Spain, where this is the case for only 10% of the sampled unaccompanied minors. In the results below, we present separately the results for unaccompanied minors (who may or not be also refugees), and for the rest of the children who are refugees or asylum seekers, as separate subsamples.

3.2.1 Unaccompanied Minors sample

The sample of unaccompanied minors (790) is the result of surveying children in reception centres or informal educational centres dedicated to this population in three countries: Greece (468), Spain (299) and Italy (23). Due to the low numbers in the Italian sample, we will focus in particular on the results for Greece and Spain. In Greece, most of these children come from Attica (292) and North Aegean Islands (80), but also from Thessaly, Epirus and some other Greek regions. In Spain, all of them come from regions not originally part of the main sampling strategy: mostly from Andalucía (148), but also from Catalunya, Canary Islands, Madrid, Cantabria (from 37-25 each), and a few other regions in Spain (Castilla y Leon, Baleare and Castilla La Mancha). A significant percentage

of these children come from rural sites (15%)⁸ and a sizeable percentage also comes from towns and suburbs (18%). The small sample in Italy comes exclusively from city centres.

Fig. 2. Number of unaccompanied minors per country and per status

The sample from all three countries is mostly composed of **middle and late adolescents** between the ages of 14-18 (28% and 57% respectively). However, in Greece and Italy there is a sizeable proportion of younger children aged 6-9 (13% and 21%), as well as early adolescents in the case of Greece (10%), which are absent in Spain.⁹ The immense majority of the sample from all three countries comprises **boys**, although this is more marked in Spain (98% in contrast to over 70% in Greece and Italy). The presence of girls is sizeable in Greece and Italy (20% and 13% respectively), but negligible in Spain (0.6%). The percentage of unaccompanied children who define their gender in another way or who prefer not to answer ranges from 13% in Italy, to 4% in Greece and 1% in Spain.

⁸ The percentages in the general sample or the refugee subsamples are 2% and 1% respectively.

⁹ In Spain there is only less than 1% of early adolescents, and of participants beyond the age scope of IMMERSE. The latter is the result of the inclusive approach employed at the level of sites, as detailed in D3.4. Participants beyond the scope are not considered in the results analysed in section 4.2 below.

Fig. 3. Age and Gender distribution of unaccompanied children sample per country

3.2.2 Refugee and asylum seekers sample

The sample of refugee/asylum seekers (802) was obtained from reception centres and informal educational centres dedicated to this population (392), and from formal schools (410), across all six IMMENSE countries. The largest samples come from Germany (387) and Belgium (178), followed by Greece (94) and Italy (82).

Fig. 4. Number of refugee/asylum children (who are not unaccompanied minor) per country and per type of site

These children come from diverse regions across all six countries (see Figure below). The resulting sample is largely urban (less than 1% were collected in rural sites) and city environments predominate (82%).¹⁰

Fig. 5. Distribution of sample of refugee/asylum seekers per region in each country

The structure of the refugee children in the sample is mostly composed of **early adolescents (11-13)**, **middle adolescents (14-16)** and **late adolescents (17-18)** representing 25%, 37% and 21%

¹⁰ Germany and Greece present the highest percentage of town and suburbs environments (28% and 17%), while this percentage is very low in the other countries (under 10%).

respectively, with small children representing 15% of the sample.¹¹ The sample has a larger representation of boys (53%) than girls (42%), and it includes 2% of children who define their gender "in another way" and 3% who prefer not to answer.¹²

Fig. 6. Age and gender distribution of children in each country

¹¹ There is a larger representation of small children in Germany (22%), early adolescents in Greece (38%), middle adolescents in Belgium (51%), and late adolescents in Italy (42%).

¹² The percentage of boys is larger in Italy (70%), while the percentage of children who define themselves or prefer not to say is larger in Spain (9% and 6%).

4 Results

4.1 Qualitative Case Study Results

This section presents a summary of key themes identified from the qualitative data. The themes are discussed in order of priority following thematic data analysis. School, and its importance in creating a sense of belonging and providing opportunities to make friends, develop language skills and experience 'childhood' is clearly evident, notwithstanding some difficulties accessing appropriate education and experiences of bullying and racism in education settings. Legal/administration challenges encountered by the young people included obtaining residency and having to follow the rules of accommodation centres, but citizenship was a valued goal for the freedoms and benefits it would bring. Friendships provide a sense of security and belonging for children and young people, with education settings seen as central to building these peer relations. The COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on participants in terms of unsatisfactory virtual learning experiences was inescapable with some participants lacking essential requirements and support structures for remote learning, many speaking of loneliness and loss of interaction with school friends but also family because of restrictions on travel. The importance of children and young people's families were highlighted along with the tensions between cultural and religious norms of the host country and the 'home' country.

In the photovoice exercises, reflecting on what helped participants feel like they belong, young people emphasised the importance of the following:

- Activities (school achievement and goals, sports etc.)
- Friendship and friendliness
- Memories both good and bad (of home, friends and war)
- Engaging with Nature (beaches, sunsets, trees and outdoors) (see figure below; photovoice example where young person felt visiting her local beach in Ireland supported her well-being and made her happy)

Fig. 7. Photo-voice 'sense of belonging' in Ireland

School and educational settings were the most important factor which supported their sense of belonging and often interreacted and intersected with these other themes identified by the participants such as the role of schools in supporting friendship. School and education are discussed in more detail in the next section.

School and Education

A myriad of issues arise in the qualitative data related to schools. Most of the participants feel good at school overall. In addition to friends and "nice" teachers, the school building and the school equipment were also decisive for their experience of well-being at school. The older the children, the more detailed, and sometimes critical, were their descriptions of their school and learning environment. Underpinning everything is the fact that schools are critically important drivers of integration for migrant children and their families (Ahad & Benton, 2018; European Commission, 2015; Martin et al., 2018; Horgan et al, 2022) through offering opportunities to learn the host language, make friends, and study with the ultimate aim of finding employment. Such opportunities are challenged by lack of access to appropriate schooling, multiple transitions to new schools, and experiences of bullying and racism in the school context (see Due, Riggs, & Augoustinos, 2016). However, a large number of Unaccompanied Minors (i.e. in Greece) were not really enrolled, and therefore their responses referred to the importance of language learning and education through informal initiatives by NGOs.

Children expressed their desire to improve in speaking the language of the host country and, depending on country of residence, learn other European languages e.g. English and German (“I want to learn more Greek. I really enjoy learning this language. I also want to learn German and to improve my English”. [Greece]). They appreciated school not only for learning opportunities, but also for providing them with the chance to make friendships upon arrival in their host countries, which was crucial regarding their sense of belonging (“(Name of primary school) is the place where I made my very first friend in Belgium and this place means a lot to me” (boy 15) [Belgium]). In the same context, school was considered by children as an essential experience of childhood (“For me justice is that children also have the right to go to school and children also have the right to learn something in school. Some girls from my country [Afghanistan] are married at the age of 14 and little children are sometimes soldiers in my country. And some of them don't have a childhood because there is war in my country for 40 years [...] Education for me is that children go to school, that children learn something in school and that they can do many things, that childhood is not destroyed.” (girl, 11) [Germany]). For children living in Greece and Italy, school was also mentioned as a means of finding employment in the future.

However, education requirements could be seen as restrictive by older children (“I don't like the outdated system of our school. I would give subjects like Art, Music, Sports etc. as optional subjects and not as a subject in which you are supposed to perform, which varies from person to person.” (girl 15) [Germany]). Alternative forms and paths for education would be seen by many children as more useful and appropriate for them (“It's great because you do things, you don't read them; there are not books, and I have always had problems with books” [Italy]). While others expressed dissatisfaction with some youth projects as less academic (“School teaches me about everything but in [youth project] there is only two classes in the day, and he [teacher] gives me drama. Drama is nothing, everyone just plays on their phone. Just give me the English class, not the art room [...]” [Ireland]).

Among other difficulties experienced in school, children mentioned a non-inclusive school culture (“As soon as you set foot in a school, at least an Italian one, you better keep your feelings out, because the teachers are not interested in your feelings. Students get anxious and suffocate. Instead of teaching us how to deal with situations, they teach us to get anxious and run away” [Italy]). They also discussed problems regarding assessment of their previous educational background in countries of origin, depriving them of the chance to continue their studies in the host country, coupled with lack of support (“I was in a closed environment; I couldn't understand

anything. I realized that I couldn't learn, the professors explained and whoever understood, understood; whoever didn't understand remained behind. (...) We foreigners, not being native speakers, we need the slowness in the lessons to be able to learn" [Italy]). On the other hand, children from specific countries totally lacked previous experience with schooling, which put further obstacles to their educational integration in host countries.

Practical barriers included difficult transitions to school due to lots of movement upon arrival in the host country and until settlement in a specific location ("I started school in Ireland in November last year [2020] but the school finished in December because of COVID. It just went 1 month, and it was very hard because it was my first time going to school. And then I moved in February. I moved to another school in April." [Ireland]). The experiences of these recently arrived migrant children highlighted the disruptive impact of frequent moves, but they were generally positive about their experiences of the mainstream school system once settled. In Greece there were issues highlighted concerning the isolated location of Refugee Camps. 'As well as issues of transport due to the isolated locations of camps away from towns (This school year, (2021/22) out of the 30 primary schools where our children are registered, school buses were found for only 12 of them") (Refugee Education Coordinator, Greece).

Bullying and racism at school was also mentioned by some children as a discouraging factor regarding integration at school. Below words of children in Germany and Greece show how school can turn to a hostile environment for migrant children.

- "I had to move five schools because of bullying. Secondly in every single school I go to, I'm not really respected or taken seriously just, they say 'she is Arab, it doesn't matter, nobody cares' [...] The school is not what you think it is. So not every single school is like you think. School is not a cool place where kids can hang out. School is also a place where you can get depression." (girl, 12) [Germany].
- "I believe it is because we are refugees. They don't want us to be in their class because they believe that we are dirty, and that we are thieves. So, they try to keep their stuff away from us. - B., 16 years old from Pakistan (focus groups in Unaccompanied Minors shelters, [Greece]).

Fig. 8. Case Study from Italy: Poster from the focus group activity.

Legal and Administration concerns

Obtaining legal residency was a key desire for older unaccompanied minors although many spoke about the difficulties associated with this process. Children were concerned regarding the lack of legal status in Spain and Greece. Obtaining legal residency was a first milestone for Unaccompanied Minors and considered as a necessary precondition for all subsequent milestones, especially education and employment.

- Boy 1: "I want to arrange the papers. If not, I can't do a course"
- Boy 2: "Of course, without the papers you can't do it."
- Boy 3: "We want to work now at 18. We want to turn 18 and work. And that's it." [Spain]
- "I need a person I can talk to and prepare my papers". (boy, 14) [Greece]

During research in Spain, Unaccompanied Minors said that although they found it hard to live in a centre for Unaccompanied Minors because they did not agree with rules imposed, but they chose to remain there because this was considered as a facilitating factor for obtaining legal documents ("I think that (the organization) is going to help us get the residence because there are many people who get out of here with it". [Spain]). Lengthy processes and requirements that are difficult to meet discouraged children's integration both in Spain and Greece and made them feel helpless regarding their future. Participants in Italy also talked about citizenship perspectives, given the benefits it brings rather than identity ("Having citizenship is great for being able to travel. Not so much to feel more Italian. Perhaps I feel more Moroccan than Italian, but Moroccan from Turin" [Italy]). In some countries Unaccompanied Minors spoke of the impact of frequent moves to different

accommodation in their host country and the impact of this movement. Qualitative research in Ireland also showed difficult transition periods for Unaccompanied Minors involving a lot of movement after arrival, which is an important barrier to socio-educational integration. “[...] I come to Limerick, but I don't find the school and after two months I come to Dublin with my family[...]” [Ireland]

Friendship and Peer Relations

Friendships were central to the children’s lives bringing a sense of belonging and security. School was a key facilitator of friendship-building (see Mohamed & Thomas, 2017). However, many referred to the difficulties in building such friendships particularly those who were newly arrived or were older on arrival in the host country. Research confirmed that school, community organisations and leisure activities are important to build and maintain friendships (“The (local youth organization) camp is where I met my friends and that means a lot to me” (girl, 16) [Belgium]). Children in all IMMERSE participating countries agreed that friendships provide a sense of belonging, security, and community (“I miss my parents, but I feel safe here. I’ve made 3 new friends so far” [Greece]), but they also shared difficulties in forming relationships in adult education centres or UAM centres. In any case, it should be noted that according to children, making friendships also depended on the amount of time spent in host country.

Fig. 9. Photovoice with Syrian Refugees in Belgium.

Impact of COVID-19

As reflected in other research on the pandemic (You et al., 2020; Lundy et al, 2021), COVID-19 has had a significant impact on the young participants lives, both in terms of increasing their experiences of educational equality and negatively impacting their mental health and overall well-being. Exacerbation of educational inequality because of difficulties in completing schoolwork independently and without additional support was highlighted by children participating in IMMERSE research in Germany, Ireland and Italy (“Yes, it's stopped everything. For me for my school I don't get nothing, I just get an email with instructions every week. I'm still busy all week because I don't understand nothing [...] sometimes I speak with my friend and he does his homework and he send it to me and afterwards I send to the teacher.” [Ireland]).

Conditions were even harder for those children living in refugee accommodation as they were lacking essential requirements and support structures for remote learning. Furthermore, they had feelings of frustration and loneliness due to restrictions, felt isolated as they had lost interaction with others and found schoolwork more difficult when online.

- “I could not follow the lessons from a distance, I did not understand well, and I was distracted. I would go into the video lessons and then put down my cell phone, leave it there on the table and go to another room. Other times I just didn't go in. Slowly I walked away. I said to myself 'this way, I can't do it'” [Italy]
- “Learning online is totally different. When you go to school you learn more and you make friends, and the communication is there as well. More speaking or communicating with other people like teachers. I was at home and the people I was staying with were at work or were busy and I was all alone. I had no friends to go with our talk with who are my age.” [Ireland]

Centrality of Family

Children being in host country with their families appreciated stability and sense of belonging (“I feel safe due to the fact that I am here with my family”. [Greece]), while those who were unaccompanied were looking forward at reuniting with their families (“They [family members] also want to come here. When I have my papers, I want them to come here with me”. [Spain]). Immigrant children in Italy also mentioned difficulty due to covid restrictions in visiting broader family abroad as a source of disappointment. Children loved spending time with their family during leisure activities in the host country and in some cases enjoyed maintaining cultural ties with host country, while in others were critical towards cultural and religious norms (“In these places we can eat Syrian food (shawarma) that we ate a lot in Syria” (Female, age 14) [Belgium], “African macho culture

bothers me. I am against it. My parents are too interested in what people think (...) They think I am against because I grew up in Italy. In reality it is the school that makes you grow (...) [you understand] that in the end we are all different” (Int. n. 1). [Italy]). These findings also highlight some of the tensions associated with children’s hybrid identities as migrants. For some of the participants they also felt that the lack of family support created more barriers for them, because the sense of loneliness, social isolation, and cultural dissonance were greater than for those children living with their family.

4.2 Results from IMMERSE survey

4.2.1 Unaccompanied children

This section presents the survey results from the sample of 790 Unaccompanied Minors who completed the IMMERSE Survey in Greece, Spain and Italy¹³. Since the sample in Italy is very small (23), the results cannot be considered as reliable, and will be shown in cursive font.

INTEGRATION RESULTS

Language and culture dimension

Unaccompanied minors report a high level **of host language competency** in Spain (64%) and Italy (83%), but not in Greece (36%). These percentages are considerably lower than the ones found in the whole migrant-background sample (except for Italy).

In terms of **intercultural ties** (i.e. feeling close to both their cultures of origin and to other groups of people, including host country), over half of the unaccompanied migrant children in Spain (54%)

¹³ For this group of unaccompanied minors, we can only analyse results from children’s questionnaires, since principal and teacher surveys only applied and were collected in formal schools. More information on the surveys is available in D3.4.

declare intercultural ties, while this percentage notably decreases to less than one-third (31%) in Greece, and to 10% in Italy. The results found on ‘feeling close to both cultures’ are better for Unaccompanied Minors only in Spain when compared to the general migrant-background population, while it worsens slightly in Greece and dramatically in Italy. A minority of Unaccompanied Minors report feeling close exclusively to their culture of origin, although the percentage increases in all three countries relative to the general sample (15% in Spain, 24% in Greece, 30% in Italy).

Well-being dimension

The majority of unaccompanied minors declare feeling **happy**, with percentages above 75% in all three countries (*Italy 100%*). Still, a significant proportion of unaccompanied children (22-24%) refer to feeling unhappy in both Spain and Greece. These results are similar to the ones found in the general migrant-background population.

Less than half of the unaccompanied minors in Greece (40%) and half of them in Spain (50%) declare having a high **sense of belonging**. This is the case for a large majority in Italy (83%), which is a better result than in the general migrant-background population. The results found slightly worsen around 8-10 percentage points in Spain and Greece.

Social connectedness dimension

The pattern of perceived levels of **support from friends and peers** by unaccompanied minors is similar in Spain and Greece, where around 40% perceive a high level of support (41% and 37%, respectively) and around half of them perceive medium support (48% and 49%, respectively). *This pattern is inverse in Italy, where around half of unaccompanied minors (52%) perceive high levels of support from friends and peers and around 40% medium support (39%).* Overall, only small proportions of children (around 9-14%) report low levels of support from friends and peers in all three countries. The results on perceived support by friends notably worsen, around 20 percentage points in Spain and Greece, when compared to the general migrant-background population. *The results are more positive in Italy and 52% of the sample report a high level of support from friends.*

In all three countries less than half of the unaccompanied children (37-45%) declare having many **friends born in a different country or from a different culture**, with a significant decrease from the general sample results. Conspicuously, children with only a few of these friends account for

more than 20% in Greece and 15% in Spain, which represents around 10 percentage points increase relative to the general sample. *There were no children in Italy in this group.*

Almost two-thirds of unaccompanied minors declare high levels of **support from teachers** in Spain (65%) and just over half of them feel the same way in Greece (53%). *In Italy the percentage gets to 91%.* When compared to the general migrant population, the trends are practically identical for Spain and Greece, *while perceived high support is considerably higher in unaccompanied migrant children in Italy (around 45% better than the general migrant population in the same country).*

Most unaccompanied children **trust teachers and schools** in all three countries. However, there is a divide between Spain, which has lower levels (around 58%) and *Italy and Greece (74% and 72%, respectively).* The levels of distrust are similar in all three countries (ranging from 9 to 14%). When compared to the general migrant population, results in unaccompanied migrant children are very similar for Italy and Greece, while there is a notable decrease for Spain in levels of trust of around 15%.

A large majority of unaccompanied migrant children also **trust doctors and hospitals** in all three countries, ranging between 68 and 73%. In fact, the health system is the most trusted among these children across the three countries. *Italy* and Greece hold the highest percentage of children trusting doctors and hospitals (70% and 73%, respectively), while Spain holds the lowest percentage, still representing over two-thirds of all unaccompanied migrant children in the country (68%). When compared to the general migrant population, trust results of unaccompanied minors are similar in Italy and Greece, while there is a notable decrease in Spain of 13%.

Most unaccompanied migrant children similarly **trust the police and justice system** with figures hovering around 52-74% in all three countries. Still, the justice system is the least trusted (behind schools and doctors) among these children across all three countries. *Italy holds the highest percentage of migrant-background children trusting police and the justice system (74%), followed by Greece (65%) and Spain (52%).* Levels of distrust in this population in Spain and Greece are considerably high, around 20% (23% and 18%, respectively). When compared to the general migrant population, trust results in Greece remain the same, *while they are notably higher for unaccompanied minors in Italy (17 percentage points) and notably lower in Spain (16 percentage points).*

BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS RESULTS

Learning and language support cluster

In all three countries, the vast majority of unaccompanied migrant children report attending **language or learning support** either at school or in the neighbourhood, with a range between 63-94%, where Spain holds the lowest result *and Italy the highest*. When compared to the general migrant population, results are dramatically better for unaccompanied migrant children *in Italy* and Greece, with the highest difference in Italy (44 percentage points), and slightly worse in Spain (9 percentage points).

A majority of unaccompanied migrant children in all three countries declare attending **extra-curricular activities** either at school or in the neighbourhood, with a range between 61% (Spain) and 69-75% (Greece *and Italy*, respectively). When compared to the general migrant population, results are higher in unaccompanied migrant children in all three countries (ranging from 2-16 percentage points).

Negative attitudes cluster

In Greece, more than half of the unaccompanied migrant children report **avoiding places for fear of being treated badly** (52%). A large minority of the unaccompanied children in Spain avoid places for fear of being treated badly, with this percentage representing 33%. *This percentage is dramatically lower in Italy, representing only 10%. While the trend depicted for Spain can also be found in the general migrant population, results are significantly better for unaccompanied minors in Italy (32 percentage points) and notably worse for this population in Greece (10 percentage points).*

A large minority of the unaccompanied migrant children report **having been bullied** at some point (28% in Greece and Spain, and 17% in Italy). Results are slightly better in Spain and Greece when compared to the general migrant population (around 5 percentage points) and notably better in Italy (22 percentage points).

4.2.2 Refugee and asylum-seeking children

This section presents the IMMERSE survey data results from the children who identified as Refugee and Asylum-seeking children (referred to as children under international protection in the survey results). In total 739 children are in this group with a very small sample from *Ireland and Spain* included¹⁴.

INTEGRATION RESULTS

Language and culture dimension

The percentage of children under international protection **reporting** having a high **language competence** varies greatly among countries (43 percentage points from lower to highest): from only 28% in Greece, the percentage increases to close to 50% in Germany and Belgium and over 60-70% in *Spain, Ireland* and Italy. Overall, these percentages are **considerably lower** than the ones found in the whole migrant-background sample, *with the only exception being Ireland*.

When asked about their **intercultural ties**, children’s results vary considerably across countries (29 percentage points from lower to highest): in Germany, Belgium and *Spain* more than a half of children under international protection report having intercultural ties (50-65%), while in Greece,

¹⁴ Caveats: Since the samples in Ireland (33) and Spain (28) are very small, results cannot be considered reliable, and will be shown in cursive font.

Refugee and asylum-seeking children who participated in the survey and were reached in experiential environments (non-school, NGO premises, etc) as a special category can provide insights for the qualitative research outcome discussing invisible children in informal education, or in UAM shelters. However, comparisons among different countries is difficult, because of the different situation of children under international protection in the 6 IMMERSE countries. The quantitative survey comprises of a few children in the overall sample, mostly from Germany (371) Belgium (156) and 90 in Greece, 72 in Italy, and even smaller samples from Ireland (33) and Spain (28) who completed the survey, mostly in informal educational settings. Their integration outcome results is significantly worse in some of the countries for example in Greece). However, if we take into account that most UAMs in Greece, who participated in the survey (476) are also asylum seekers or refugees, then the results should be read with that caveat.

Italy and Ireland this percentage decreases to between 36-40%. Overall, these percentages are **in line** with the results obtained for the whole sample of migrant-background children, and only **Germany** presents a **notably higher** percentage of children under international reporting intercultural ties.

Well-being dimension

The majority of migrant background children under international protection across countries report **feeling happy**, with percentages above 72% in all countries. Overall, the differences between these results when compared to the whole sample are **very small** (less than 5 percentage points).

Around a half (40-53%) of children under international protection across countries report a high **sense of belonging in school**. This percentage notably decreases in Belgium where only 35% of children report a high sense of belonging. These results are **in line** with the ones obtained for the whole sample, and only present *small differences in the countries with small samples of children under international protection (from 8 percentual points in Italy and Spain to 11 in Ireland)*.

Social connectedness dimension

The percentage of children under international protection reporting high **support from friends and peers** varies **notably** across countries (14 percentage points from lower to highest): while in Greece and Germany over half of these children report high levels of support, in Italy, Belgium and *Ireland* these percentages decrease closer to 40%. Overall, these results present **small differences compared with the whole sample** of migrant-background children (around 5-11 percentage points), except for Greece, where the percentage is similar.

More than half of the children under international protection report having many **friends born in a different country or from a different culture** in Germany, Greece, Belgium and *Spain* (60-67%). Only in *Ireland* and Italy this percentage falls below 50%. These results present **notable** differences with the ones obtained for the whole sample of migrant-background children in Spain and Greece, and **small** differences in the other countries: overall, children under international protection report more often having many friends born in a different country or from a different culture.

Over half of the children under international protection in all countries surveyed report high **support from teachers**, with small differences emerging across countries (13 percentage points from the lowest to the highest). The differences compared to the whole sample of migrant-background children are small (around 10 percentage points) and point to similar patterns.

Most migrant-background children under international protection **trust teachers and schools**. These results vary considerably compared to the ones obtained in the whole sample (5 to 16 percentage points from the lowest to the highest), although the trend does not change substantially. Overall, children under international protection report a higher percentage of trust in all countries *except in Spain and Ireland, which are the countries with smaller and less representative sample sizes*.

Although more than half of the children under international protection report **trusting doctors and hospitals** in all countries, the differences compared with the whole migrant-background children sample are considerable (6 to 20 percentage points from the lowest to the highest) in all countries except for Germany, which presents similar trust percentages. Overall, children under international protection report trusting doctors and hospitals in a lesser extent than the complete group of migrant-background children.

Most migrant-background children under international protection **trust the police and justice system** with figures hovering around 50-60% in all countries. Compared to the whole sample of migrant-background children, children under international protection report a considerably lower percentage of trust in *Spain, Ireland,* and *Greece* (from 9 to 18 percentage points), while there are notably higher percentages in *Italy, Germany* and *Belgium* (from 5 to 11 percentage points).

BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS RESULTS

Learning and language support cluster

Most children under international protection declare attending **language or learning support** either at school or in the neighbourhood, with a range of between 60-78%. These results contrast notably with the ones obtained for the whole sample of migrant-background children: children under international protection results vary less across countries (18 percentage points from the lower to the higher compared to 34 in the whole sample), and overall attend language or learning support either at school or in the neighbourhood in a greater extent.

More than half of the children under international protection report attending **extra-curricular activities or after-school learning** either at school or in the neighbourhood. *Spain and Ireland, with the smaller and less representative sample present respectively the lowest and highest percentages of attendance*, while in the rest of the countries the percentage of children under international protection attending extra-curricular activities or after-school learning either at school or in the neighbourhood ranges from 62-74%. Overall, and overlooking the smallest samples, these results are slightly higher and in line with the ones obtained for the whole sample.

Negative attitudes cluster

When looking at the reported **perception of negative attitudes**, two different patterns emerge in the sample of children under international protection. In Southern European countries such as Italy, Greece, and *Spain* they report fear of being mistreated in a lesser extent than children in Belgium, Germany and *Ireland*. Still, a troublesome range from 23% to 43% of children under international protection report feeling fear of being mistreated across countries. These results indicate more variability across children under international protection than in the whole sample (with differences ranging 20 to 10 percentage points respectively), although overall they declare not fearing being mistreated more often than the complete group of migrant-background children.

When looking at the reported **experiences of bullying**, two different patterns emerge in the sample of children under international protection. More than a half of the children report not to have experienced bullying in Germany, Italy, and *Spain*, while in Belgium, Greece and *Ireland* there are higher rates of bullying (range from 53 to 65%) reported by the children under international protection report. These results indicate more variability across children under international

protection than in the whole sample (with differences ranging 24 to 16 percentage points respectively), although except in Italy, they declare having experienced bullying more often than the complete group of migrant-background children.

The next section will map the results discussed on the to IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators.

5 Mapping the findings on the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators

The findings align closely with the dashboard of 30 indicators of refugee and migrant children’s integration and this section will map the findings from Unaccompanied Minors, Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children onto the dashboard of indicators.

5.1 Integration results

Access to Rights

As evidenced by relevant studies¹⁵ most Unaccompanied Minors arriving in Europe are over 15 years old, which is when education becomes non-obligatory in many European countries. This is similar to the profile of the Unaccompanied Minors which participated in the qualitative cases studies for this study. A number of these participants in the qualitative research discussed the difficulties they faced in accessing education and in particular formal education which they felt would support their employment prospects. Issues identified included lack of appropriate education routes, the poor quality of the education they received, their current migration status or lack of status impacted their ability to register for education and frequent accommodation moves

¹⁵ See Panteion on Homeless UAMs in Greece, 2022, AIDA 2023, UNICEF 2023

impacting their ability to enrol in education. As shown both by IMMERSE qualitative research case studies, supported by literature review (GCR-TdH, 2022 for Greece) and UNICEF Country Reports for UAM in Europe's, because of their journey, these children face more mental health issues and have general knowledge gaps because they are often out of school for many years.

Language and Culture

The majority of Unaccompanied Minors report high levels of competence in the main language of their country of residence, which is important to support their social and academic engagement with some variability within the sample, for example, Spain has significantly higher levels of reported **language competency** than Greece. Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children reported lower levels of host language competency than other migrant children in the IMMERSE survey including unaccompanied minors. Extensive research has consistently highlighted the significant influence of the host country's language skills on the disparity in achievement between migrant and native individuals. Various studies, including Turney and Kao (2009) have emphasized the pivotal role of linguistic proficiency in this gap. In the qualitative research many of the participants expressed a desire for high levels of host country language competency to support their educational inclusion and highlighted the barriers that they faced due to language difficulties. As a result, it becomes crucial to prioritize language support to aid Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children in acquiring the language spoken in their new country, especially if they have never followed any school education. By doing so, we can effectively foster their integration into the host society.

In terms of **intercultural ties**, the research findings pertaining to how Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children maintain their cultural identity post migration and their development of intercultural competencies, present a complex situation that is influenced by the unique migration histories of various nations and by the status of migration. When comparing unaccompanied minors with first- and second-generation migrant children the results found that 'feeling close to both cultures' was most positive for unaccompanied minors in Spain, less positive in Greece while children in Italy had the poorest outcomes in this indicator. A minority of unaccompanied minors report feeling close exclusively to their culture of origin, although the percentage increases in all three countries relative to the general sample (15% in Spain, 24% in Greece, 30% in Italy). For the Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children in Germany, Belgium and Spain more than half declare having intercultural ties (50-65%), while in Greece, Italy and Ireland this percentage decreases to 36-40%. In countries with a longer history of immigration, the majority of children with a migrant background report having intercultural connections. However, in countries

with more recent waves of immigration, like Spain, Greece, and Italy, the percentage decreases in favour of those who do not feel closely connected to their culture of origin. Overall, there is a significant minority of migrant children who do not feel a strong connection to people from their culture of origin. This observation holds significance since establishing connections with both the host country and the country of origin is crucial for fostering favourable educational and psychosocial outcomes. (See also D.3.4 report). The qualitative research also showed that children felt it was important maintaining their cultural ties with their country of birth, for example through food but some of them also spoke of challenges in accommodating their parents' cultural heritage with host country norms.

Well-being

The majority of Unaccompanied Minors declare feeling **happy**, (75%+) in all three countries. Still, a proportion of Unaccompanied Minors (22-24%) report feeling unhappy in both Spain and Greece. These results are similar to the ones found in the general migrant-background population. The results are very similar for Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children. Age and gender play a role in happiness levels reported by all migrant and non-migrant groups with happiness decreasing as children grow older. Migrant boys, express higher levels of happiness than migrant girls. Results on sense of belonging found that in most countries less than half of the Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children and Unaccompanied Minors had a high **sense of belonging**. Boys are slightly more likely to report a higher sense of belonging than girls, with a decline in this sense of belonging as children age. The qualitative data presents a more nuanced experience on the well-being of Unaccompanied Minors. While many were happy to be in their host countries, they also spoke of the impact of stress on their well-being and the impact of the uncertainty about their future as having a negative impact on their well-being.

Social Connectedness

The dimension of social connectedness pertains to the nature of children's social networks involving significant individuals and institutions. Conducting direct research on social connectedness with children is imperative for gaining insights into the experiences of Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children. Concerning **peer support and connectedness**, the pattern for Unaccompanied Minors is that around half of them perceive medium levels of support from their friends. When it comes to children under international protection who report high support from friends and peers, the results vary across countries; while in Greece and Germany over half of these children declare high levels of support, in Italy, Belgium and Ireland these percentages decrease closer to a 40%. These results present small differences compared with the whole sample. Overall,

only small proportions of children (around 9-14%) report low levels of support from friends and peers in all three countries. For Unaccompanied Minors, in Greece, Spain and Italy, less than half (37-45%) declare having many friends born in a different country or from a different culture, with a significant decrease from the general sample results. More than half of the Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children declare having many friends born in a different country or from a different culture in Germany, Greece, Belgium and Spain (60-67%) and lower rates in Ireland. In the qualitative data the participants spoke about the importance of friends and in particular the role of education and schools in supporting them to make friends.

In relation to interconnectedness with teachers, the majority of Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children reported high levels of support from their teacher's similar to other migrant and non-migrant children in the survey. The results on **institutional trust** demonstrate high levels of trust in societal institutions, with healthcare institutions being the most trusted. Most Unaccompanied Minors **trust teachers and schools** in all three countries. However, Spain has lower levels (around 58%) compared to *Italy* and *Greece* (74% and 72%, respectively). When compared to the general migrant population, results in Unaccompanied Minors are very similar for Italy and Greece. Most Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children **trust teachers and schools**. A large majority of Unaccompanied Minors **trust doctors and hospitals** in all three countries. When compared to the general migrant population, trust results for Unaccompanied Minors are similar in Italy and Greece, while there is a notable decrease in Spain. And although more than half of the Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children **trust doctors and hospitals** in all countries, the differences compared with the whole migrant-background children sample are considerable (6 to 20 percentage points from the lowest to the highest) in all countries except for Germany, which presents similar trust percentages. Most Unaccompanied Minors similarly trust the **police and justice system** with figures hovering around 52-74% in all three countries. For Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children, the results indicate a slightly lower level of trusts than other migrant groups (50-60%). The justice system is the least trusted (behind schools and doctors) among these children across all three countries. Gender and age also exerted an influence on the levels of institutional trust reported by the study participants.

5.2 Barriers and Facilitators

Political leadership

As evidenced in the qualitative results, residency was a key desire for older unaccompanied minors although many spoke about the difficulties associated with this process. Children in Spain, and Greece in particular expressed concerns about lack of legal status and how this impeded their other rights. Obtaining legal residency was a first milestone for the Unaccompanied Minors in the study and considered as a necessary precondition for all subsequent milestones, especially education and employment. Obtaining legal status was experienced as a challenging and lengthy process for many of the Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children and accessing citizenship required lengthy procedures and often required support by NGOs, including, in some cases, participants feeling they needed to live in NGO facilities to regularise their migration status. Many children in focus group discussions and in the surveys took a pragmatic approach to these requirements. Still regularization and uncertainties lead to stress, low self-esteem, and inability to plan for the future. Issues identified by research participants include some children being unable to cope in the school environment and becoming marginalized. The living and legal situation in some of the consortium countries is putting unaccompanied children at a significant disadvantage in the school environment. This is evident in the qualitative research findings of IMMERSE, but also documented by other studies on Unaccompanied Minors (Panteion Homeless Unaccompanied Minors in Greece, 2022, AIDA Reports, 2023).

Learning Supports

In all IMMERSE countries, migrant children had higher attendance rates at **after-school learning or language support programmes** compared to their non-migrant peers and this is also the situation for Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children. For Unaccompanied Minors in Greece, Spain and Italy, the vast majority declare attending **language or learning support** either at school or in the neighbourhood. These results show higher participation rates in these programs for Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children compared to other migrant children in the survey. More Unaccompanied Minors in Greece attend language learning support than other migrant groups in Greece which is striking as this group also have the lowest levels of host language competency compared to other groups. A majority of Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children reported attending **extra-curricular activities** either at school or in the neighbourhood. Overall, and overlooking the smallest samples, these results are slightly higher than those for other migrant groups in the sample.

Negative Attitudes

Regarding **children's subjective perceptions and experiences of mistreatment** by others, a large minority of migrant-background children in the overall IMMERSE survey fear being treated poorly, leading them to avoid certain places. A large minority of the Unaccompanied Minors in Spain **avoid places for fear of being treated badly**. While this trend depicted for Spain can also be found in the general migrant population, results are significantly better for unaccompanied minors in Italy and notably worse for this population in Greece (52%). In the sample of Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children two different patterns emerge. Children in Southern European countries such as Italy, Greece, and Spain report a fear of being mistreated to a lesser extent than children in Belgium, Germany and Ireland. These results indicate more cross-country variability among Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children than in the whole sample (with differences ranging 20 to 10 percentage points respectively), although overall the majority of this group report not fearing being mistreated more often than the complete group of migrant-background children. A large minority of the Unaccompanied Minors declare having been **bullied** at some point (28% in Greece and Spain, and 17% in Italy). Notably, in the sample of Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children, two different patterns emerge. More than half of these children reported not having experienced bullying in Germany, Italy, and Spain, while in Belgium, Greece and Ireland the rates of bullying reported by this group of children was higher. In the qualitative research some of the participants spoke of their direct experience of harassment and bullying and highlighted examples of racism which they faced in school and in their communities including one Syrian child who moved schools five times due to bullying and racism.

6 Conclusions: supporting the socio-education integration of Unaccompanied Minors, Refugee and Asylum-Seeking Children

Multi-method approaches were used in gathering data from groups of migrant children who are likely not to be represented within the largescale IMMERSE survey. Thereafter, findings from the IMMERSE qualitative data were merged with the quantitative findings from the survey, offering a more in depth perspective on these cohorts of children and young people. The qualitative case studies used a mixed-methods approach including individual interviews, focus groups, observation, photovoice and mapping to elicit the lived realities of children and young people from a range of migrant backgrounds, with an emphasis on those especially vulnerable, including unaccompanied

minors, newly arrived migrant children, and other particularly vulnerable groups. In particular, the journaling, photovoice and mapping methods produced highly personal and detailed narratives/accounts by children and young people with specific experiences of being a migrant. Engagement with nature, for example, emerged strongly from the photo-journaling activities as an important facilitator of young migrants' sense of belonging and the participatory research methods used in the case studies allowed the children to identify their own sense of belonging in a creative way.

The research findings reveal a complex and multifaceted landscape of socio-educational integration for children with migrant backgrounds in European education settings. While there are positive trends, such as positive levels of happiness and participation in support programmes, there are also challenges, including language disparities, varying levels of belonging, experiences of bullying and difficulties in accessing residency and citizenship.

Participants in the research expressed high levels of institutional trust in schools and the majority felt supported by teachers, indicating the important role that schools play in supporting the integration of these young migrants. The quantitative results found higher levels of engagement with learning and language support for these two migrant groups (Unaccompanied Minors, and Refugee and Asylum-Seeking children) compared to other migrant children in the research. However, the findings on host language competencies for Refugee and Asylum-seeking children indicate the need to provide additional supports to these groups to support language proficiency.

While the findings on school were generally positive, for some participants there were negatives associated with access to appropriate education settings. These included informal education centres offering pathways with limited educational value, and incidences of bullying and racism across sectors. In the quantitative research a minority of the Unaccompanied Minors had experienced bullying, and this was also reflected in the qualitative research. Being subjected to bullying has been associated with reduced happiness for migrant background children, as highlighted by Correa-Velez et al. (2010). Also Unaccompanied Minors experienced a lower sense of belonging than other migrant and non-migrant groups in the study. Complex immigration processes and uncertainty about their residency status negatively impacted on Unaccompanied Minors and Refugee and Asylum Seeker Children's their education and mental health.

Friendship was a key factor sustaining migrant children and young people in the host country. Friendships provide a sense of security and belonging for children and young people, with education settings seen as central to building these peer relations. However, findings on interconnectedness and diversity of friendship demonstrate that Unaccompanied Minors have less

diverse friendship groups and potentially fewer social bridges than other migrant children and non-migrant children.

The central importance of family in providing a sense of stability and belonging is highlighted in the data while the tensions between family culture and religion and that of the host country are evident as seen elsewhere in the literature (Dyson, 2015). IMMERSE findings found that family enhanced feelings of belonging through relationships, food, and shared leisure activities.

Furthermore, IMMERSE findings on lower levels of institutional trust for health and justice institutions among Refugee and Asylum-seeking children underscore the importance of exploring these intersections and using this evidence to identify additional avenues for support and policy intervention.

Finally, COVID-19 emerges as a disruptor for many of the young participants in this research with negative experiences of education, relationships with friends, and family, including family who lived in another country.

Overall, the findings are similar to those reported in the literature that schools are critically important drivers of integration for migrant children and their families (Ahad & Benton, 2018; European Commission, 2015; Martin et al., 2018; Horgan et al, 2022) through offering opportunities to learn the host language, make friends, facilitate educational attainment and qualifications and in supporting future employment opportunities. However, IMMERSE research also demonstrates that these opportunities are challenged by lack of access to appropriate schooling, multiple transitions to new schools, and experiences of bullying and racism in school contexts for some of the participants, particularly the most vulnerable. These areas need to be addressed to support socio-educational integration. Addressing these issues will contribute to more inclusive and equitable educational environments for all children.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Appendix 1. Qualitative Case Study Sample and Research Settings

Italy: Qualitative research in Italy took place in four non-formal education environments across the country. Researchers realized that even though all settings were located in disadvantaged areas, different cities reflect very different environmental contexts even with respect to the distribution of migrants and foreign students.

Spain: In Spain, the research team chose to conduct research in an experiential learning environment dedicated to Unaccompanied Minors, which provides one of the most complete care systems of the country, accompanying the youngsters since their arrival in the territory, up to their full independence in some of the cases. This part of the research took place mainly in a village, but also in the provincial capital. In the second Spanish centre for Unaccompanied Minors, which is the only one publicly owned and managed in the region.

Germany: Qualitative research conducted in German non-formal education settings involved collaboration with an NGO promoting intercultural coexistence with a variety of educational and cultural events/ workshops and social counselling.

Ireland: The Irish research team put a deliberate focus on unaccompanied minors and young people 'ageing out' of the education system (16-18 years old) or outside the formal education system as the experiences of these groups would be harder to capture in the larger IMMERSE survey. The setting was located in the capital, which is the region hosting most Unaccompanied Minors, and its objective is the empowerment of separated children and young people to live independent and healthy lives and to integrate into and participate fully in society. In the second Irish setting the Irish team identified an organisation which provided support to Roma children, most of whom were born in Ireland. The Roma community are recognized as a particularly disadvantaged and marginalised community in Ireland, along with indigenous Irish Travellers (Department of Justice and Equality, 2017).

Greece: Researchers in Greece focused on unaccompanied minors and newly arrived refugee children with an age range between 14 to 17 years old, living in Camps, safe zones, or shelters, who were following non formal education and extra-curriculum activities, in NGO premises. The first

group of children were accompanied by their parents, while the second consisted of male Unaccompanied Minors supported through the provision of psychosocial services. Both groups had not been enrolled in the Greek school system. In most of the reception centres or shelters and other informal educational premises included in the overall sample, children had a similar profile. Most centres had several language and professional training programs and shelters or other accommodation for children over 18 to ensure they are not left alone after reaching legal age which, in Greece, implied exiting the reception system without further assistance.

Belgium: Research in Belgium focused on newly arrived migrant children from Syria receiving services from a non-profit organisation to aid the integration of migrants through sports, social and cultural activities; and a second group of newly arrived from various countries including Ukraine in an OKAN Unit attached to a secondary school.

Appendix 2 In **Ireland**, UCC carried out a combination of focus group interviews and individual interviews with Unaccompanied Minors and young people “ageing out” of the education system. The researchers used an interview schedule based on the IMMERSE Dashboard Indicators examining: participant's legal status; access to compulsory education; access to health care; competence in host language; competence in mother tongue; maintaining their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences; life satisfaction / happiness; sense of belonging; friends and peers; teachers; trust in and engagement with key institutions; academic skills; school completion. These were supplemented with additional questions relating to the impact of COVID-19 on their education and lives more generally, as well as their plans for the future. The fieldwork for the first case study took place virtually and comprised one paired interview online via zoom with two male participants, and one individual interview online via zoom with a female participant with a translator/interpreter on the call. The second case study comprised two in-person focus group interviews, photo-elicitation and mapping activities with a group of Roma children. The first focus group comprised icebreakers, discussions on the key dashboard indicators and concluded with a request for them to take photos before the next meeting. Key prompts given for photography included: (1) places where you spend your time, (2) places where you feel safe or unsafe, (3) how do you get around? walk, bus, cycle, (4) where do you go with friends? (5) are there any centres or organised activities for you in your area? The follow-up meeting with the girls began with a discussion of the photos taken. Each group was then given a selection of photos & asked to

sort the photographs into the key themes. The sessions concluded with them creating 'integration maps' showing their 'world' and their sense of belonging in their local community using posters, markers, photos, 3d models, photos and google image photos (see Figure below).

Fig. 10. Mapping Activity with Children in Ireland

A combination of in-person focus group interviews and individual interviews with Unaccompanied Minors was carried out by the team in **Spain**. Three focus groups and 15 in-depth interviews were held with Unaccompanied Minors, along with eight interviews with staff members working in an organisation providing care for Unaccompanied Minors. Semi-structured interviews with Unaccompanied Minors focused on their views of how the reception and integration process affects their lives. The research team also visited and conducted participant observation in a reception centre for unaccompanied minors, observing the rooms, common spaces for leisure and the restaurant where they spend the majority of their time, the interactions between the centre's staff and the children, as well as factors like the level of privacy these children enjoy during their stay, that could not be identified exclusively through the other applied techniques.

Researchers in **Greece** also chose to organise focus group discussions with two groups of children from migrant backgrounds who were participating in non-formal education (with a mix of recently arrived refugee and asylum-seeking children and unaccompanied minors). The focus groups utilised post-it activities and discussion centred on education, well-being, cultural values, friends, integration and acceptance in the host country. Music and other ice breaking games were used to create an atmosphere of trust and facilitate more open discussions. School experience was

discussed, relationship within family, friends, experiences of racism, bullying. And during interviews with researchers, topics discussed were their educational needs, school choices, motivation to study, aspirations, achievements and expectations concerning adulthood, uncertain future, their need to have a “guardian” or a “mentor” to assist and support them with their choices.

In their first qualitative study, researchers in **Italy** led a focus group discussion on the project topics, particularly looking at the school experience, relationships with family and peers, and the urban area in which participants live. Participants in the focus group also took part in a dairying exercise where they shared with the researchers via email further opinions and experiences concerning the three broad areas addressed during the focus group. A paired interview with two adolescents with migratory backgrounds was also conducted building on the material collected through the dairying activity. This facilitated the exchange of opinions and sharing of experiences between the two interviewees, in order to grasp the possible different perspectives linked to the different identity factors, such as gender and origins. In the subsequent qualitative studies, researchers interviewed a total of six young people with migrant backgrounds on topics such as educational needs, school choices, motivation to study, aspirations, achievements and expectations concerning adulthood, and sense of belonging and social capital.

Researchers in **Belgium** utilised the Photovoice method with a group of five young people with a migrant background from Syria and another group of 5 young people in an OKAN Unit attached to a secondary school. The young people collected images on their phones or drew pictures of places where they spend their time. These included places like school, community and after school activities, and anywhere that gives them a sense of belonging in their community. They provided brief explanations or phrases with the photos as to why they are significant to their sense of belonging. The young people could work together or individually to compile their photo journals. The photographs and captions were compiled via WhatsApp and email.

Photovoice was also employed by researchers in **Germany** to enable a creative approach in discussing the experiences of four refugee and asylum seeker children. Participants were asked to take pictures that express their perspective, views and feelings around their learning experiences. Researchers guided participants to focus their images on wellbeing and belonging, educational achievements, and learning support. The questions used to guide participants were drawn from the IMMERSE Dashboard of Indicators. In a follow up focus group, participants were asked to select their three favourite images (see Figure below). The images were then used as a stimulus in a group

discussion. Discussions and reflection centred around the topics of why the photographs were chosen, what makes them meaningful, and what participants thought of each other's images. The second case study used a combination of a brainstorm map and survey co-creation with children to inform a focus group discussion. The key foci were - school, best ways of learning, and teachers.

Fig. 11. Photovoice activity information sheet Germany

8.2 Appendix 2 Study Information Sheet and Child Assent Forms for Qualitative Research

IMMERSE Information Sheet for Children & Young People's Participation in Qualitative Research

IMMERSE is an international project funded by the European Commission. IMMERSE stands for “Integration Mapping of Migrant and Refugee Children in Schools and Other Experiential Environments in Europe.”

Purpose of the Study: To find out how we can help children, especially children from migrant backgrounds, feel happy in school in Ireland.

What will the study involve? The study will involve your participation in a focus group, on 1st and 8th December at UCC. Researchers from our team at UCC will conduct two sessions will take approximately 1 hrs and 30 minutes. These will include a focus group interview, some journaling on your experiences of school and/or taking some photos for a mapping exercise.

Why have you been asked to take part? You have been asked because you are involved in the Cork STAR project.

Do you have to take part? No, participation is voluntary. You will be asked to sign an assent form. You can also stop participating in the study, even if you have already agreed, and you do not have to give a reason. After you have finished, you can still change your mind up until ten years after the project is finished (which will be in November 2022).

Will your participation in the study be kept confidential? Yes, absolutely! Your answers will be anonymised, which means that no one will know that they are yours. Your name or any other identifying information about you will not be used.

What will happen to the information you give? Your data will become part of a securely stored database with the data from your group and other children and young people in Ireland and Europe! The IMMERSE team will use this data to help make recommendations to schools, communities, and governments about how to help children and young people feel like they belong at school.

What will happen to the results? The results will be presented in a report to the European Commission. We also hope to publish some of the findings in articles and books.

What are the possible disadvantages of taking part? We don't envisage any negative consequences for you in taking part.

What if there is a problem? At the end of the process, we will talk with you to see how you found the experience and how you are feeling. If you feel upset, you should talk to your teacher or contact the researcher below.

Who has reviewed this study? Approval has been given by the UCC Social Research Ethics Committee (srec@ucc.ie, and all members of the research team visiting schools have been garda vetted).

Any further queries? If you need any further information, you can contact:

Shirley Martin (Principal Investigator) s.martin@ucc.ie
Deirdre Horgan (Principal Investigator): d.horgan@ucc.ie
Reana Maier (Postdoctoral Researcher): reana.maier@ucc.ie

Child Assent Form

I.....agree to take part in the research study.

I understand what the study is about and it has been clearly explained to me.

I am participating voluntarily.

I undertake to maintain the confidentiality of the group.

It's fine if I drop out of the study, and I do not have to give any reasons for this.

I understand that the information collected are for research and teaching purposes only for the IMMERSE project. I have the right to see these data, change them, or ask that they be deleted and not used. I can withdraw permission to use the data from the study at any time up until ten years after the project finishes, in which case the material will be deleted. If I change my mind and want to withdraw after a report has been published, my material cannot be removed from the reports, but the research team will not use it in any future work or analysis.

I understand that nobody will know it's me in the results or report because my name or any other identifying information will not be linked to my survey answers.

Name: _____ Date:

- Yes, I do consent.
- No, I do not consent.

8.3 Appendix 3: Qualitative Template for Case Study Data Collection

UCC Qualitative Research template for return of data

Participant Sample (one must be with UAM’s; both with 10 years+ age group)

- o Unaccompanied minors
- o Migrant children (first and/or second generation)
- o Newly arrived migrant children
- o Refugee and asylum seeker children
- o Other (please specify)
- o Age range
- o Number of participants
- o Gender breakdown

Brief description of the setting (150-200 words. Please omit name of organisation and other identifying information)

- o Context of intervention
- o Duration of the programme/establishment
- o Geographical area (outline the reasons for choosing this/these location/s)
- o Objectives of the setting
- o Methodology/ approach to working with service users
- o Funding model

Research Methods (please attach relevant documentation eg. focus group/ interview guide)

- o Focus group
- o Other, please specify

Brief Description (500 words)

Data analysis (500-1000 word thematic⁽ⁱⁱ⁾ analysis supported by children’s quotes⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾)

Compliance with one or more of the Dashboard Outcomes (tick all that apply)

O1.1.1 Children's legal status	
O1.1.2 Access to compulsory education	
O1.1.3 Access to health care	
O2.1.1 Children's competence in host language	
O2.2.1 Children's competence in mother tongue	
O2.2.1 Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences	
O3.1.1 Children's self-esteem	
O3.1.2 Children's life satisfaction / happiness	
O3.1.3 Children's sense of belonging	
O4.1.1 Friends and peers	
O4.1.2 Teachers	
O4.1.3 Institutions	
O5.1.1 Children's academic skills	
O5.2.1 Children complete compulsory education	

O5.2.2 Children remain in (formal) education beyond compulsory levels / Access to (formal) non-compulsory education	
O5.2.3 Types & levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended	

Additional comments

8.4 Appendix 4: IMMERSE Your Voice Counts Survey designed by Youth Participants (DOZ, Germany)

IMMERSE - Your Voice Counts (DOZ Germany)

We want the voices of migrant children and youth to be heard in research and policy. In the long run, we want to contribute to children and young people being actively involved in decisions that affect their own lives and the development of their community.

Your answers will be treated strictly confidentially, and the evaluation and publication will be anonymous. Your answers can therefore not be linked to your person later.

Question 1: How old are you?

Question 2: What gender are you?

- female
- male
- diverse(transgender/non-binary/prefer not to say)

Question 3:What does education mean to you?

Question 4: Do you learn new things in places other than your school?

- Yes
- No

Question 5: What other places do you learn new things?

Question 6: Do you also learn through social media or other online platforms?

- Yes
- No

Question 7: Which social medias or online platforms do you use for learning?

- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Tiktok
- Twitter
- Pinterest
- Reddit
- Others

Question 8: How are you doing at school? What do you like? What don't you like at all? What would you like to change?

Question 9: What are you good at? Which subjects or topics do you like best?

Question 10: How do you enjoy learning the most?

Question 11: What support helps you learn the most? What do you need to learn well?